

Изменение парадигмы управления российскими вузами в текущих геополитических условиях

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. В современных внешнеполитических условиях вузы РФ столкнулись со множеством внутренних и внешних вызовов, которые стимулировали пересмотр аксиологических ориентиров и механизмов управления высшим образованием в стране. Представляется целесообразным разработать адаптивный алгоритм анализа влияния сложившейся ситуации на управление вузами, продемонстрировав его применение конкретным примером.

Цель статьи заключается в рассмотрении теоретических и практических основ влияния текущих геополитических условий на философию управления российскими вузами (на основе опыта Финансового университета).

Материалы и методы. В основу методологии исследования вошла модель черного ящика, которая позволяет рассмотреть административные подразделения вуза как комплекс взаимосвязанных элементов, реагирующих на условия внешней среды.

Запросами в систему выступают, в частности, санкционное давление и интенсификация реформирования образовательной системы. Ответ системы проанализирован при помощи контент-анализа и SWOT-анализа. Для визуализации полученных количественных данных использован метод диаграмм.

Основными материалами исследования выступили нормативные акты, задающие направленность управления высшим образованием в РФ; новости на официальном сайте Финансового университета, локальные нормативные акты и внутренняя информация вуза.

Результаты исследования представлены научным обоснованием прямого и опосредованного влияния текущих геополитических условий на философию управления российскими вузами; проработкой пути анализа организации деятельности вузов и формулирования рекомендаций по ее оптимизации.

Заключение. Начавшиеся в феврале 2022 г. внешнеполитические действия РФ стали точкой бифуркации в развитии философии управления высшим образованием. Особого внимания требует его работа в тесном переплетении с актуальными внешне- и внутривнутриполитическими интересами страны.

Разработанный алгоритм может быть использован для совершенствования административного обеспечения научной и образовательной деятельности российских вузов в сложившихся геополитических условиях, а также для постановки и решения задач проблемного поля «политика – философия управления высшим образованием» в рамках научных исследований.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

российское высшее образование, философия управления образованием, аксиология образования, образовательная политика, международное сотрудничество вузов, специальная военная операция

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

A paradigm shift in the management of Russian universities in the current geopolitical conditions

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. In modern foreign policy conditions, Russian universities have faced many internal and external challenges. They stimulated the revision of value orientations and mechanisms of higher education management in the country. An analysis of the scientific literature shows that many researchers raise only certain aspects of this urgent problem. It is important to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the actual challenges through the prism of the philosophy of higher education management. Moreover, it is advisable to develop an adaptive algorithm for analyzing the impact of the geopolitical situation on the management of universities, demonstrating its application by a specific example.

The aim of this study is to explore the theoretical and practical foundations of the impact of the current geopolitical conditions on the management philosophy of Russian universities. The Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation serves as an example for the analysis.

Materials and methods. The "black box" model allows us to consider the administrative structures of the university as a complex of interrelated elements that respond to external conditions.

The requests to the system (university) are, in particular, sanctions pressure and the intensification of changes in the educational system. The system's response was analyzed using content analysis and SWOT analysis. The method of diagrams was used to visualize the obtained quantitative data.

The main materials of the study were regulations in the field of higher education management, news on the official website of the Financial University, internal information of the university.

The results of the study include a scientific justification of the impact of the current geopolitical conditions on the philosophy Russian universities management (on the example of a Financial University); an analysis of the administrative processes in the Financial University and formulation of recommendations.

Conclusion. The period of the special military operation became a bifurcation point in the development of the philosophy of higher education management in the Russian Federation. The functioning of higher education in close connection with the relevant foreign and domestic political interests of the country requires special attention.

The usability of the obtained results lies in their potential application for improving the administrative processes in Russian universities. The results can also be used to formulate and solve the problems of the field "politics – philosophy of higher education management".

KEYWORDS

Russian higher education, philosophy of education management, axiology of education, educational policy, international universities partnership, special military operation

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INTRODUCTION

The analysis of domestic and foreign scientific research literature shows that today the problem of the influence of a special military operation on the philosophy of management of Russian higher educational institutions has not yet acquired a comprehensive theoretical and practical study. For the most part, this is due to the complex nature and incompleteness of the political conflict involved. Nevertheless, there are some studies on certain aspects of this issue.

The first area of research on the impact of a special military operation on the management of Russian universities is their international activities. As difficulties associated with the current geopolitical situation are overcome, a new awareness has emerged regarding the significance of the activities of international services at universities in terms of attracting foreign citizens and exporting education [1, pp. 23-24]. Russian universities are faced with a situation in which their internationalization should be carried out, on the one hand, taking into account the emerging new identity of the university as an entrepreneurial one (this idea was largely introduced by Western model), on the other hand, based on the idea of strengthening the national higher education system [2, p. 134]. Currently, the goals and conditions of the organization of international activities in higher education are most consistent with the nationally oriented model, which is beginning to displace globalist approaches [3, p. 743]. This trend has not only positive, but also negative assessments. For example, the formation of a "de-internationalized" Russian higher education is interpreted as a result of the country's "aggressive and isolationist policy" [4, p. 6].

The political conflict that has arisen leads to a complication of relations with a number of international partners of Russian universities. At the same time, there is a strengthening of scientific and academic ties with the states that Russia is reorienting towards in the context of a special military operation. The new geography of international cooperation is represented by the strengthening of ties with universities in the CIS, Asia, Africa and Latin America against the background of the freezing of contacts with Western countries [5, p. 554]. This fact leads to an increase in the popularity of research aimed at identifying the features, problems and prospects of cooperation between Russian universities and relevant partners.

The second line of research is based on the increasing need to strengthen traditional values among students, which is a particular expression of the deepening participation of the state in the management of education. There is a struggle with the established postmodern ideology of education, the priorities of which are associated with "egocentric interests in which the idea of eternal values and public benefit is on the periphery" [6, p. 68]. Today, attention is focused on the need to build Russia's "own ideological platform for higher education" [7, p. 21].

A significant role in this area is occupied by research involving statistical data, which aim to determine the specifics of the formation of students' civic attitudes and their perception of patriotism. There are mixed trends in this regard. Despite the presence of several studies conducted after the start of the special military operation that demonstrate an increase in the patriotic sentiments of Russian youth, this trend is lower among students, which is reflected in an increase in stress, decreased confidence in socio-political institutions and actors, and the influence on the dynamics of the migration sentiments of this social category [8, p. 9]. The opposite trend is also shown by the fact of the spread of anti-patriotic narratives and discourses in social networks, as confirmed by monitoring of information flows [9, p. 44]. It becomes necessary to conduct research on this topic, using the examples of new regions in Russia. The relevance of forming the civic identity of young people living in the territories of the new subjects of the Russian Federation is determined by the requirements of regulatory documents, the targets of state youth policy, the need to adapt and integrate this category of youth into the Russian socio-cultural and economic space [10, p. 53].

The question of how higher education should instill the value of patriotism in students today is being actualized. It is noted that, in general, today the educational environment is designed and creates conditions for students to acquire civic experience [11, p. 170]. Attention is focused on the need to move away from the understanding of patriotism as an abstract social phenomenon and the relevance of real social practices aimed at forming an individual patriotic consciousness [12, p. 95].

The third direction follows from the second and is devoted to the analysis of changes in educational modules, which should convey traditional values and demonstrate a special path of development of Russia against the background of a special military operation. Such changes were reflected in the formation of new academic disciplines ("Fundamentals of Russian Statehood", "History of Religions of Russia"), an increase in the hours of existing ("History of Russia") courses, the creation and adjustment of teaching aids, the revision of professional competencies of teachers at the documentary level and a departure from Western patterns of drawing up educational programs [13]. From the perspective of the axiology of education and educational management, the significant development was the introduction of the "Fundamentals of Russian Statehood" course. The content of this module is guided by a civilizational approach. Meanwhile, the question of the degree of philosophical ideas are included in the course curriculum remains open [14, p. 113].

The fourth area includes research on the topic of the sovereignization of Russian education in the context of geopolitical turbulence and the increasing complexity of cooperation with Western countries. Steps towards sovereignization are expressed in raising the problem of reforming the higher education system of the Russian Federation in order to gradually move away from the Bologna system, on the one hand, and return the advantages of Soviet education, on the other. The need for such reforms has been repeatedly stressed at the official level. In a Message to the Federal Assembly in 2023 The President of the Russian Federation stated that the education system needs "a synthesis of the best practices of the Soviet system and the last decades".

The Bologna Process, as a state intervention in the field of higher education, was aimed at creating a single European higher education area, and a comprehensive restructuring was planned to be carried out precisely within the framework of a single concept (the Bologna System) [15, p. 252]. However, it is noted that in most Russian universities, this was implemented mainly as a formality, which is why a real departure from the Bologna system in Russia is not possible [16, p. 142, 147]. Attempts to completely restore the Soviet system are also illusory, since its removal from the socio-cultural context can lead to the system's unviability [16, p. 147].

Anyway, in the modern scientific and socio-political discourse of the Russian Federation, the idea of the inefficiency of the Bologna system is beginning to become more widespread. The political basis that prompted Russia to sign the Bologna Declaration has disappeared [17, p. 14]. In the context of the conflict in Ukraine and sanctions, the need to adapt the norms of world-class universities in Russia to the changing context and new political goals began to distort such norms [18, p. 47]. This factor had a strong impact on the development of the higher education management philosophy, highlighting the need for its comprehensive review.

It is also important to emphasize a number of other aspects, the analysis of which can be found to a greater extent at the level of direct universities management, rather than at the level of scientific research.

Firstly, the causes, course, consequences and prospects of conducting a special military operation aroused considerable interest in the scientific community and began to have a direct impact on the subject of scientific research carried out in higher educational institutions. It is becoming increasingly necessary to conduct a scientometric analysis of the transformation of research topics, taking into account the above trend. This will make it possible to determine the involvement of universities in the discussion of a number of aspects related to the current political conflict.

Secondly, the procedure for admission to Russian universities has changed. Legislative innovations made it possible to consider the participation of a citizen in a special military operation as an individual achievement and establish a separate quota for admission at the expense of budget allocations for such citizens. In addition, universities of the Russian Federation were recommended to provide additional benefits to a number of categories of citizens: reduce tuition fees, provide installments under a contract for the provision of paid educational services. These measures stimulated a change in the axiological priorities of higher education management, demonstrating its increasingly close relationship with the country's foreign policy course.

Thirdly, after the start of the special military operation, an unprecedented number of sanctions were imposed on Russia, which affected the possibilities of organizing the universities activities,

primarily in the scientific and educational fields. For example, there are changes in the software used by universities, opportunities for publication in foreign scientific journals, etc.

Taking into account these circumstances will allow us to more fully reveal the theoretical and practical grounds for the influence of a special military operation on the philosophy of management of Russian universities, which is the purpose of this study.

In this article, the Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation serves as an example for analysis. The authors used a set of methods, among which content analysis and SWOT analysis play a central role. The changes in the organization of scientific and educational activities of the university were considered, which made it possible to formulate recommendations for optimizing administrative processes taking into account the current geopolitical situation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research methodology is based on the application of a systematic approach and a black box model. The consequences of the current conflict (the "entry" of the system) have an impact on the management of universities, while the latter react in a certain way to these consequences (the "exit" of the system). Despite the publicity of information about the administrative structure of many higher educational institutions, not all the processes taking place inside it are open to the researcher. We believe that the classical black box model can be adapted to the research problem and presented as follows (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 A model of the impact of a special military operation on the management of higher education institutions

In this case, the university acts as a system responding to environmental conditions. Requests to the system are, in particular, changes in the foreign policy situation and the sovereignization of the Russian educational system during the period of a special military operation. The authors analyzed the system's response using general scientific methods of observation, comparison, deduction and induction, synthesis and analysis. The special methods used in the study include content analysis and SWOT analysis.

Content analysis is used to determine changes based on information published on the Internet (including the official website of the Financial University), regulations governing the organization of scientific and educational activities of the university. The authors also used internal information provided by the Financial University upon request. All this acts as the main research materials.

In turn, SWOT analysis, as a classic tool for studying the internal and external environment of an organization and its functioning at the "exit", is used to develop practical recommendations for optimizing university management in the field of scientific and educational activities based on the identified strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats of such activities in the current geopolitical conditions. This method makes it possible to consolidate the recorded changes within the framework of educational management and, on this basis, formulate conclusions about changes in the philosophical educational paradigm. In the paper this paradigm is defined as the whole of scientific attitudes to the educational process, ideals and values of education, ways of organising education, etc., in a particular culture/society [19].

RESULTS

The results of the study allow us to state that in the current geopolitical conditions there is a change in the philosophical paradigm of management of Russian universities, which today is increasingly intertwined with the political sphere.

Regarding the organization of scientific activities, we note that the observed deterioration of relations with Western countries has affected the publishing capabilities of Russian scientists, including researchers at the Financial University. Some foreign publications have changed their publication policy towards authors from Russia. This could not but affect the priorities of Russian researchers and university management in relation to the problem of publication activity in foreign journals.

For example, within the framework of performance indicators of scientific departments and temporary research projects of the Financial University, there were opportunities to replace Scopus and Web of Science publications with publications included in the Russian Science Citation Index (RSCI). In addition, the focus has shifted to publications of those states that are currently more willing to enter into scientific cooperation with Russian researchers and are members of Scopus and Web of Science. Financial incentives from the university are provided for publications indexed by these systems and related to quartile I or II, which allows to maintain the incentive for university staff and students to publish research in foreign journals and select suitable ones.

The change in international scientific relations has also affected the list of foreign partner organizations of the Financial University that carry out scientific research together with the university. Let's demonstrate this fact using the example of the international temporary creative student groups (ITCSG) 2020-2024. (Fig. 2).

ITCSG consists of students and a supervisor from the Financial University, as well as students and a supervisor from a foreign educational partner organization. Together, they prepare a scientific study on a competitive basis, which is defended before the commission at the end of the academic year.

The above data confirm that after the start of the special military operation, the scientific relations of the Financial University began to be rebuilt. On the one hand, the countries that took a skeptical attitude towards conducting a special military operation (USA, Finland, Armenia) stopped carrying out research work within the framework of ITCSG together with the Financial University. On the other hand, there is a reorientation towards other partner countries. Kazakhstan remains a relatively stable partner in ITCSG. In recent years, there has also been an increase in cooperation with Belarus and the Kyrgyz Republic. In the 2023-2024 academic year, several applications were submitted for the creation of ITCSG together with universities in China and Uzbekistan.

The next area of influence of the special military operation on the organization of scientific activities of the Financial University is its inclusion in the subject of scientific research.

Figure 2 Countries of foreign educational organizations involved in the implementation of the ITCSG at the Financial University in 2020-2024.

The main source for quantitative analysis of research carried out by university staff is the Scientific Activity Plan for 2024. It outlines the topics of applied and fundamental scientific research, a number of which are related to the conduct and consequences of the current conflict. The topics were grouped by the authors and presented in diagrams (Fig. 3).

The above data show that more than 40% of the topics of applied and more than 30% of fundamental scientific research carried out by the Financial University within the framework of a state assignment are somehow related to the conduct and consequences of a special military operation. Such topics are not widespread, but they are also present at the level of dissertation research.

Let's turn to the topics of research carried out by students of the Financial University within the framework of temporary creative student groups (TCSG) in 2022-2024 (Fig. 4).

TCSG is an association of students under the scientific supervision of an employee of a Financial University who carry out research work commissioned by an external organization (most often a Russian one).

The above data show that more than 7% of TCSG topics in the 2022-2023 academic year and more than 5% of TCSG topics in the 2023-2024 academic year are related to the conduct and consequences of a special military operation. The lack of percentage growth for the 2023/2024 academic year is largely due to a sharp increase in the total number of TCSG, but not a decrease in interest in this issue.

Figure 3 Groups of topics of applied and fundamental scientific research carried out by the Financial University in 2024 according to the state assignment

Figure 4 Groups of TCSG topics carried out by the Financial University in 2022-2024

Scientific research, the topic of which is related to the conduct and consequences of a special military operation, is carried out by employees and students of Russian universities, including outside the above-mentioned types of projects. Therefore, the authors consider the implementation of in-depth scientometric analysis of publications on this topic in electronic library systems to be a promising topic for a separate study.

An important consequence of the special military operation for the Financial University is the restructuring of not only scientific, but also educational ties with foreign universities. In this regard, two aspects should be considered: academic mobility of Financial University students abroad and academic mobility of international students to a Financial University.

In 2022-2024, the Financial University suspended the implementation of a number of two-degree and inclusive education programs. Monitoring of the university's official website during this period showed that at the initial stage, comments on the temporary suspension of cooperation were added to some existing programs, and then the programs were completely removed from the official website. First of all, these changes apply to states that support the Ukrainian side during a special military operation. However, at the moment, students of the Financial University still have a choice of programs for studying abroad.

As of the end of the 2023/2024 academic year, the official website of the Financial University contained information about 4 dual degree programs with China, opportunities for inclusive education in Argentina, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Brazil, Vietnam, India, Indonesia, China (where there are most educational organizations to choose from), Malaysia, Mongolia and Serbia. The presented list of countries confirms the statement formulated earlier about the reorientation to educational organizations of other partner countries.

Students from universities in China, Uzbekistan and Mongolia were able to study at the Financial University under two-degree programs. However, there are many foreign young people studying at the university who are not studying on the basis of two-degree programs. To form a more complete picture of the contingent of foreign students, let us refer to the data presented below (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 The number of foreign students at the Financial University in 2020-2024 academic years

These data demonstrate that, despite the special military operation, in the period from 2020 to 2024, the number of foreign students at the Financial University has continuously increased in all faculties.

The top 20 leaders in the number of foreign students at the Financial University over the past 4 years have consistently included the CIS countries: Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan, Kyrgyzstan, Armenia, Moldova, Belarus, as well as Vietnam, Mongolia, China, Ukraine, Bulgaria, Abkhazia, South Ossetia, Turkmenistan, Syria and Afghanistan.

The period of the special military operation affected the change in the top 20 leaders only insignificantly. This fact demonstrates the stability of the Financial University's international relations with the educational organizations of the above states. In addition to the efforts of the Financial University in the framework of its international activities, several other factors that strengthen these ties should be highlighted. Firstly, an important factor is Russia's close cooperation with the CIS countries in the economic sphere, including the role of the Russian Federation as a significant importer of foreign labor resources. Secondly, a number of ongoing political, including ethnopolitical conflicts – the Afghan, Syrian, Abkhaz, the conduct of a special military operation, etc. – they are a factor stimulating academic mobility to Russia due to the feeling of insecurity among foreign students in their native country.

The fact of the low popularity of the Financial University among students from Western countries both before and after the start of a special military operation confirms that the deterioration of relations with them can be considered not as a sharp change introduced by the period of this conflict, but as a long-term trend. The Financial University cooperates closely with Russian government agencies (especially in the field of graduate employment) and has not received the stigma of a Western-oriented university. However, international prestige remains on the other side of the scales: this is evidenced by the strategic initiatives that are enshrined in the program for the development of the Financial University until 2030. And that's not just about the international prestige, but also about understanding the role of academic mobility programs in "increasing the competitiveness of university graduates in the labor market" [20].

The next direction is changes in the content of educational courses.

Firstly, from September 1, 2023, an extended course on the History of Russia is provided in all curricula. Regardless of their specialization, students study this course for 144 academic hours. The expediency of taking this measure is largely due to the intensification of attempts to falsify Russian and world history during a special military operation, a change in the state course on the formation of historical memory, the need to strengthen patriotism and other traditional values of the Russian people.

Secondly, starting from the same year, the course "Fundamentals of Russian Statehood" was included in the curricula for the 1st year of the bachelor's degree. The module is a tool for shaping the political consciousness of modern youth, used to strengthen feelings of citizenship and patriotism, as well as to form students' understanding of the role of Russia at the current stage of historical development. Axiologically, the module is a continuation of such normative documents as Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 07/02/2021 No. 400 "On the National Security Strategy of the Russian Federation"; Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 05.09.2022 No. 611 "On approval of the Concept of Humanitarian Policy of the Russian Federation abroad"; Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 09.11.2022 No. 809 "On approval of the Foundations of State Policy for the preservation and strengthening of traditional Russian spiritual and moral values".

Thirdly, the sanctions pressure after the start of the special military operation became an incentive to strengthen the state policy on ensuring technological sovereignty. The details of this course are contained in the Resolution of the Federation Council of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2023 "On Ensuring the scientific and Technological development of the Russian Federation in order to achieve technological sovereignty". Educational programs that are particularly in demand from the point of view of ensuring technological sovereignty (for example, the programs "Applied Machine Learning", "Data Analysis", "Information Security", etc.) began to appear and popularize at the Financial University. They correspond to the List of specialties and areas of higher education training corresponding to the priority areas of modernization and technological development of the Russian economy.

Another area of influence is connected with the sanctions pressure – the revision of the software used. It is possible to note several changes in this regard at the Financial University. The implementation of the task of replacing foreign IT products was expressed at the beginning of the transition from the Windows operating system to the Astra Linux system. The transition is fraught with difficulties at the level of administrative and technical costs and the level of teaching. Nevertheless, the new operating system began to be used on many computers of the university. The

sanctions also affected access to information databases provided through the library and information complex. This influenced, in particular, the research of a number of laboratories of the Financial University. However, the necessary services are provided to fulfill the main tasks that arise during the scientific and educational process.

A significant consequence for the Financial University was the change in the admission rules for educational programs. The official website of the university contains information on the establishment of a separate quota for citizens undergoing military service, subject to the participation of such citizens in a special military operation. Moreover, to support the needs of the special military operation, the Financial University makes regular charitable donations. Detailed information about these donations can be found on the university's official website.

Based on the results of studying the impact of a special military operation on the organization of scientific activities at a Financial University, the authors compiled SWOT analysis table (tab. 1).

Table 1

SWOT analysis of the organization of scientific activities at a Financial University during a special military operation

<p>Strenghts</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A system has been created to encourage staff and students to publish in international journals; 2. The presence of links with foreign educational organizations in Kazakhstan, Belarus, the Kyrgyz Republic, China, Uzbekistan and other countries friendly to Russia, including in the implementation of research within the ITCSG; 3. Active implementation of research works on a special military operation at the levels of applied, fundamental scientific research on a state assignment. The availability of such studies within the TCSG. 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reducing the possibilities of publishing scientific research in journals of Western countries; 2. Weakening of ties with foreign educational organizations in Western countries, including in the implementation of research within the framework of ITCSG; 3. A low number of planned dissertation studies devoted to a special military operation, including its course, consequences and prospects.
<p>Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of new or withdrawal of existing Financial University journals to the level of indexing in Scopus and (or) Web of Science; 2. Strengthening international scientific ties both in the direction of the countries that Russia is reorienting towards during the special military operation, and in the direction of Western countries. In particular, an increase in the number of research projects carried out within the framework of ITCSG; 3. An increase in the number of dissertation research and ongoing scientific events, within the framework of which the course and (or) consequences of a special military operation are considered, including ways to solve the problems that arose against the background of this conflict. 	<p>Threats</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A decrease in the quality of scientific research, including dissertation research, in the event of the arrival of a wave of participants in a special military operation entering graduate and doctoral studies at a Financial University within the framework of new special benefits for this category of applicants; 2. Further weakening of scientific ties with Western countries and, as a result, weakening of the international prestige and international competitiveness of the Financial University in the absence of effective measures to solve this problem.

Then, based on the identified consequences of the impact of a special military operation on the organization of educational activities at a Financial university, a SWOT analysis table has also been compiled (tab. 2).

Table 2

SWOT analysis of the organization of educational activities at a Financial University during a special military operation

<p>Strenghts</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stable growth in the number of international students at the Financial University, which means an increase in its popularity abroad; 2. The availability of stable flows of international academic mobility, including from the CIS countries, countries of the Asia-Pacific region; 3. Close ties with government agencies, including in the field of internship organization; 4. Availability of progressive educational programs corresponding to the list of priority areas of higher education specialties. Active participation in strengthening Russia's technological sovereignty; 5. Preventive adaptation of employees and students to alternative IT products, which corresponds to the vector of import substitution; 6. The availability and active use of a fund-raising system to support participants in a special military operation, which forms a positive image of the university from the point of view of the state. 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decrease in the number of international academic programs where students of the Financial University can study (due to the deterioration of relations with Western countries); 2. Reflection of sanctions pressure on access to foreign IT products, including information databases.
<p>Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthening international educational ties both in the direction of the countries that Russia is reorienting towards during the special military operation, and in the direction of Western countries. 2. Intensification of work within the framework of import substitution of foreign IT products: promotion of own developments of students and employees of the Financial University; 3. Intensification of the PR campaign informing about the existence of an organized fund-raising to support participants in a special military operation, as well as informing about the work already done in this direction. 	<p>Threats</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The growing discontent of students applying for budget places at a Financial university, in the event of the arrival of a wave of participants in a special military operation entering budget places within the quota (this circumstance can reduce the chances of admission to budget places on the basis of a Unified state exam); 2. Further weakening of educational ties with Western countries and, as a result, weakening of the international prestige and international competitiveness of the Financial University in the absence of effective measures to solve this problem.

The results of the analysis allow us to provide a list of recommendations for optimizing the administrative processes of the university.

1. Strengthening international educational and scientific ties both in the direction of the countries that Russia is reorienting towards during the special military operation, and in the direction of Western countries. Expanding the number of international educational programs, concluding new cooperation agreements, intensifying the invitation of foreign teachers and sending teachers of the Financial University to foreign educational partner organizations, increasing the number of research projects carried out within the framework of ITCSG, etc.;

2. Creation of new or withdrawal of existing Financial University journals to the level of indexing in Scopus and (or) Web of Science and continuation of the policy to increase the number of publications of students and university staff in foreign journals;

3. An increase in the number of dissertation research, scientific events and published works, which consider the course and (or) consequences of a special military operation, including ways to solve the problems that arose against the background of this conflict.

4. Using close ties with the state as an advantage, make an active contribution to the promotion of traditional values, the patriotic agenda, and the idea of technological sovereignty (including in the field of IT) through a series of educational, scientific, and business events.

DISCUSSION

In this study, changes in the management philosophy of Russian universities were analyzed on the basis of scientific research literature (in the introduction), and on the example of a Financial University (in the results). From the authors' point of view, the algorithm used can also be applied to analyze changes in the administration systems of other higher education institutions.

The results obtained are consistent with the work of a number of authors already mentioned, who are considering the new geography of scientific and educational cooperation of Russian universities [5]. Also, the results line up in a trend according to which the involvement of Russians in the implementation of patriotic nurturing over the past five years is gradually increasing [21, p. 1375]. The example of a Financial University has demonstrated the focus of Russian education on instilling traditional values, which are actively considered by many Russian scientists. The statement that the pursuit of geopolitical interests makes the internationalization process at governmentally-controlled universities more difficult and controversial also demonstrated its reasonableness [22].

An analysis of foreign literature has shown that the need to change the educational paradigm is currently being discussed not only in relation to Russia. It is noted that the "Western triumphalism" that occurred after the collapse of the USSR ultimately led to the fact that globalization became the "buzzword for a process of integrating capitalist logics into all domains", including education [23]. Currently, the thesis of the need to "escape the trap of the capitalist logic" is being popularized in foreign discourse [24]. Neoliberalism and its partial manifestations in education are criticized for "shifting universities' missions in another direction by creating winners and losers", as well as for "the potential inability of graduates from disadvantaged backgrounds to access the career opportunities they desire, the claim of disempowerment by academics, and the disadvantaged status of humanities" [25; 26]. The need for a comprehensive revision of neoliberalism in education in the "post-neoliberal era" is emphasized [27]. As applied, for example, to South Africa, a similar necessity is expressed in the term of departure from the "Eurocentric epistemic hegemony" [28].

Thus, the scientific discussion of the need to change education paradigms away from previously set Western patterns has now acquired an international character. Today, a new "idea of the university" is being actively considered, and, as Tight's scientometric research shows, Russia plays a certain role in its development [29]. This circumstance fits into the logic of the study and confirms the previously considered intensification of the Russian discourse on the problem of changing the educational paradigm.

Today, special attention is paid to the importance of the national education system in nation-building [30]. Despite criticism towards the emphasis on this fact by a number of scientists, it describes the situation that is developing in Russian education.

As prospects for further analysis, the authors consider it necessary to conduct dissertation research devoted to a comprehensive analysis of the impact of a special military operation on the management of higher education. A comparative analysis of this impact on the activities of various higher education institutions in Russia and abroad also requires special attention.

The expansion of the field of application of such a method as content analysis is possible through the use of specialized media monitoring systems, which would allow not only to track a larger volume of changes in the management of universities, but also to analyze the number of scientific and educational events dedicated to the topic of a special military operation and conducted at various universities, to determine the image of this process in the views of students and university staff. Sociological surveys can also complement the range of methods used.

CONCLUSION

Consideration of the process of transformation of the philosophical paradigm of management of Russian higher education institutions in the current geopolitical conditions, including the example of a Financial University, allowed us to draw several important conclusions.

Firstly, the special military operation had a significant impact on the management of Russian universities. It not only deepened the trends that were brewing even before it began, but also served as an occasion to raise questions about the most rapid change in the focus of university management (for example, in terms of the need to foster patriotism and protect traditional values, strengthen technological sovereignty, move away from the Bologna system, etc.). In other words, the period of special military operation has become a bifurcation point in the development of Russian higher education.

Secondly, today we are witnessing a fundamentally important trend that requires continuous monitoring, in which Russian higher education works closely intertwined with the foreign policy of the state. This is especially clearly reflected in the areas of organization of scientific and educational activities of universities, which is demonstrated by the example of a Financial University.

Thirdly, the use of a systematic approach in studying the influence of geopolitical conditions on the philosophy of university management has a high descriptive potential. It provides an orderly representation of the process of changing university management systems by identifying the factors and the sides that influenced it; determining the consequences and prospects of this influence. According to the authors, in further research on similar topics, it is advisable to apply and develop a systematic approach, expanding the range of examples and methods used within it.

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